

GENETIC TYPES OF EVAPORITES OF THE ARAL SEA CATCHMENT AREA

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Modern continental evaporites within the Aral Sea catchment area are widely developed and are represented by a wide variety of salt occurrences. We conducted a monographic district description of them earlier (Rubanov, 1977), Some issues of modern halogenesis were considered in numerous publications of the author (Rubanov, 1960-86; Rubanov and co-authors, 1964-87).

Pioneers in the study of lake salts, salt marshes, saline soils, and mineral waters are G.B.Leonov (1886), N.A.Di"o (1914) A.G.Bergman (1935,1946), A.G.Zens-Litovsky (1938, 1939, 1957, 1968), K.M.Feodotyev (1945), B.A., Beder (1958), I.N.Feofarova (1940), V.A.Kovda (1946) and others.

Continental salt accumulation occurs under the influence of a number of factors (aridity, composition of catchment rocks, water-salt availability, etc., see Chapter 4), leading to the formation of numerous accumulative forms. The main forms of modern salt deposits according to F.Lotze (1957) the following: salt fades, salt marshes, salt crusts and salt lakes (lake salts). In our understanding, salt crusts are salt marshes, and the concept that Lotze puts into the definition of a salt marsh is a shore. Salt fades are formed on the surface of rocks in subaerial conditions due to the evaporation of mountain moisture (residual salinity) from them, which moves to the surface of rocks under the influence of insolation.

The description of salt accumulation sites can be carried out in accordance with classifications based on the various principles themselves. Thus, salt accumulations can be subdivided:

- 1) According to the degree of watering of the salt accumulation area: subaerial and subaqueous;
- 2) According to the types of natural waters involved in salt accumulation - atmospheric, surface (temporary, permanent) and underground (groundwater, pressure);
- 3) According to the morphotectonic features of salt accumulation sites: accumulations in erosive basins (open and closed) and accumulations at the bottom of tectonic depressions;
- 4) According to the genetic types of salt accumulation forms, salt marshes (above-ground and subsurface), shores and salt deposits of lakes;5) по химическим типам солей - на карбонатный, сульфатный и хлоридный;
- 5) according to the mineral composition of salts - gypsum mirabilite (tenardite), halite, astrakhanite, epsomite and others (in various combinations);
- 6) according to the landscape-geomorphological features of lake salt accumulation, they are divided into central lake (central water-bearing) and priozernye (drive-bearing), etc.

The main genetic varieties of salt accumulation forms, established by the author according to their relationship with the surrounding rocks, are summarized in the figure, where saline (soil), shore and lake facies types are highlighted).

1-Salt, 2- silt, 3-salt crust, 4-water-resistant rocks (clays), 5-aquifers (sands, etc.), 6-weak water-resistant rocks (loess, etc.), 7-ancient consolidated (Paleozoic) rocks, 8-groundwater level and direction of water flow.

It should be said that in the literature there is a discrepancy in the understanding and terminology of modern salt accumulations. Often, a salt marsh is understood as a saline soil with a thin crust of salt, as well as a multi-meter salt deposit. The author systematized the available information on these formations and specified (using the example of the studied region) the concept for each of the identified types of continental salts – salt marsh, shore, salt deposit.

Each of these types, in turn, is subdivided (depending on the geomorphological and facies-lithological features of the salt accumulation site) into more detailed varieties of salt accumulations. Further systematization of salt accumulation sites is carried out according to the type of natural waters involved in their water-salt nutrition.

References:

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